

A regional atlas of metocean conditions over the Brazilian coast

Renan Braga Ribeiro¹, Gabriel Vieira de Carvalho¹, Pedro Santos²,
Palle Martin Jensen², Sara Jackson²

¹ DHI Water & Environment Inc, Lakewood, CO, USA;

² DHI A/S, Hørsholm, Denmark

rbro@dhigroup.com, gvdc@dhigroup.com, psan@dhigroup.com, pje@dhigroup.com, sja@dhigroup.com

ABSTRACT

Accurate metocean design conditions are the essential input for offshore energy projects from feasibility all the way to detailed design. This paper introduces a new regional atlas composed of spectral wave and 2D hydrodynamical models covering the Brazilian and Uruguayan coasts with unprecedented coverage and spatial resolution. The motivation to deliver an accurate and validated metocean atlas in the region comes from the increasing prospects of seabed usage for offshore wind energy generation. The spectral wave and 2D hydrodynamic models were setup using MIKE Powered by DHI with the domain divided in two regions, called north and south, to cover the Exclusive Economic Zone where offshore wind projects are planned and to account for the distinct atmospheric and ocean flow patterns observed in each distinct area. The validation of both models was done in-situ measurement data from 16 stations for integral wave parameters, 12 for water levels and 2 for currents. Moreover, satellite altimetry measurements were also used to quantify the precision and accuracy of significant wave height results across the entire domain. The validation results point to a high-quality atlas for both integral wave and ocean parameters, with a mean bias (and mean root-mean square error) across all measurement stations for significant wave height of -0.02m (0.29m), peak wave period of -0.24s (1.79s), water level of 0.02m (0.13m) and depth-averaged current speed of 0.01 m/s (0.14m/s). The regional atlas is now hosted online and commercially available inside DHI's Metocean-On-Demand portal. The validation work presented herein shows the suitability of the atlas' underlying data to be used as an input for multiple applications including front-end engineering design of planned offshore wind farms.

Keywords: Offshore wind; Metocean; Design conditions; spectral wave; hydrodynamics.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Brazilian Institute of Environment and Renewable Natural Resources (IBAMA) has received requests for environmental permits for more than 200GW worth of planned installed capacity by offshore wind energy projects¹. Even with superposition of neighboring projects, the ambitious plans outlined by offshore wind developers show the need for accurate and precise design conditions to lower the project risk and provide future leased areas with a metocean database suitable for input into certifiable front-end engineering design (FEED) [1].

With a favorable bathymetric profile along the continental shelf, low incidence of tropical storms combined with a wind climate dominated by trade winds (which yield potentially high annual capacity factors), the Brazilian Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) is highly attractive for bottom-fixed offshore wind turbines, considered a mature and developed technology globally. The federal policy, currently being discussed by

¹ [Mapas de projetos em licenciamento - Complexos Eólicos Offshore — Ibama \(www.gov.br\)](http://www.gov.br)

the government, regarding spatial planning and seabed lease is the main hindrance for the kick-off of this technology in Brazil. With the intention to clarify these aspects, the Company of Energy Research (EPE in Portuguese) has published two technical reports outlining international procedures both for spatial planning [2] and lease royalties [3] in several countries where offshore wind is mature.

From early-phase feasibility studies to detailed design, meteorological and oceanographic (metocean) conditions must be characterized using long-term modelled datasets which are validated using local in-situ measurements [1]. The primary objective of this study was to develop and validate high-resolution hydrodynamic and spectral wave models that deliver comprehensive metocean data for Brazil's coastal regions. The output of these models aims to provide a regional metocean atlas suitable to support planning, design, and operation of planned offshore energy projects, providing critical information on waves, currents, and other oceanographic parameters.

Currently for the Brazilian coast, wave and ocean datasets are available from global reanalysis models ran and maintained by independent intergovernmental organizations. An example is The European Center for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) who provides both wave (WAM) and ocean (ORAS5) reanalysis models. However, such models have a low spatial resolution and tend to lack accuracy for a detailed characterization of local sea-state conditions, especially in coastal areas and shallow waters where offshore wind projects are being planned. Figure 1 presents an example of the model mesh around the first proposed offshore wind farm (OWF) in Brazil, Asa Branca I. ECMWF's WAM model (left panel) has only one grid cell around the OWF, while DHI's global wave model (middle panel) has a flexible mesh that follows the coast and covers the OWF with three grid cells.

Figure 1: Illustration of Asa Branca I planned wind farm area (purple polygon) with model mesh of ECMWF's global wave model (left), DHI's global wave model (middle) and DHI's Brazil regional model (right).

Although other commercial hindcast wave and ocean models exist in the market, none has gone to the spatial resolution presented herein (Figure 1, right panel). With a spatial resolution in the order of 3km around the planned Brazilian OWFs, this regional atlas has the ambition to provide high-quality metocean data sufficient to be applied in certifiable FEED studies, with the potential to reduce load assessments and ultimately reduce the levelized cost of energy (LCOE) for a given business case (see Figure 3).

This paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides the theoretical background, discussing the specific physical ocean flow processes pertinent to each domain region that should be captured by a regional model. Additionally, this section addresses the current limitations in global wave model databases, highlighting the need for more refined regional models. Section 3 outlines the methodology used to setup the models, including the selection of the domains, boundary conditions and the validation data from publicly available sources. Section 4 presents the two main results of this work, namely the validation results, with several statistics to quantify accuracy and precision of the main output parameters, and an overview of the resulting statistics of significant wave height across the entire domain, which demonstrates a concrete application of the atlas for planning purposes. Finally, discusses potential further applications and developments of the regional atlas, and conclude the study.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Acknowledging the main dynamical oceanographic and meteorological processes that drives and impacts the waves and currents in the studied area is vital to set up the modeling effort. Without extending too much – as this is not the intention of this paper – we briefly discuss the dynamic process that are the most relevant when setting up a wave and currents modelling effort for the Brazilian offshore wind projects areas.

Several large-scale atmospheric systems influence both wave and hydrodynamics. In north Brazilian coastal areas, the Intertropical Convergence Zone (ITCZ) plays a crucial role, with its seasonal shifts impacting the northern Brazilian coast by altering wind directions and intensities. In the period from June to November, the ITCZ reaches its northernmost position exposing the coastal zone to the southeast trade wind system intensification, while in the period of December to April the ITCZ reaches its southernmost position, exposing the shoreline to the northeast trade winds and waves influence. Additionally, long-fetch waves generated by cyclones in the north Atlantic propagate to the north Brazilian coast mainly from December to April [4]. Along the south and southeastern Brazilian coast, the waves and currents on continental shelf are mostly influenced by semi-stationary atmospheric systems such as the South Atlantic Subtropical High Pressure System (ASAS), which generates persistent southwestward winds generating consistent wave conditions and the passage of transient frontal systems which disrupts the stable conditions established by the ASAS, leading to abrupt changes in wind patterns and wave conditions [5].

Moreover, understanding the influence of large-scale ocean currents on wave propagation is essential, especially in the northern region where the North Brazilian Current (NBC) presents high intensity ($>1\text{ms}^{-1}$) thus potentially exerting a strong influence in the wave propagation. The NBC's strength and direction significantly impact wave patterns, creating complex interactions that can alter wave height and direction. A global assessment of the impact of ocean currents on modeled wave fields by several authors showed that a systematic positive bias of the modeled wave height against altimetry data can be seen, and that including ocean currents in the wave model considerably reduces the reported positive bias [6]. Although presenting a global scale assessment, the authors pointed that this effect can be observed in strong west boundary currents such as the North Brazilian Current (NBC).

When comparing H_{m0} , altimetry derived against the ECMWF ERA5 wave reanalysis [7], a notable positive bias is observed along the northern Brazilian coast, potentially linked to the high intensity NBC. Additionally, a negative bias in the Para-Maranhão basin is evident, likely due to poor bed roughness parameterization and tidal currents representation in this global scale model (Figure 2).

It can also be noted that the bias along the east/southeast/south Brazilian ocean is less prominent and organized, which can be related to the less intense and persistent characteristics of the west boundary ocean current along these regions, known as the Brazil Current (BC). This current can also result in strong currents ($\sim 1\text{ms}^{-1}$) associated with transient mesoscale eddies.

Figure 2: Comparison (BIAS) of H_{m0} derived altimetry data and ECMWF-ERA5 reanalysis results.

Regarding Continental Shelf Circulation, where targeted OWF projects are located, besides western boundary currents (BC and NBC) acting near the shelf break, there are basically three other forcing mechanisms for currents in this long shelf: (1) wind stress, (2) tides, and (3) near coast baroclinic pressure gradients. The importance of each one varies spatially and temporarily, in both along-shelf and

cross-shelf directions [8]. Furthermore, on the southeast continental shelf the sub inertial response to wind forcing is essentially barotropic [9]. For the hydrodynamic model in this study, it is important to note that the targeted OWF projects falls within the continental shelf and are mainly influenced by barotropic processes, with wind stress, tides, and river discharges being the most relevant factors. Consequently, a 2D barotropic hydrodynamic model was employed. Although extensively validated against all available water level and current measurements, it is important to note that the results of the HD model do not represent the baroclinic current systems and should be used with caution.

In summary, the careful assessment of the oceanographic and meteorological processes is a crucial step when producing an accurate regional metocean atlas. In the present modelling effort, significant attention was given to the preliminary selecting the set of models' inputs, including the representation of ocean currents in the wave models.

3. STUDY METHOD

In this section, the spectral wave and 2D hydrodynamic models are briefly described. The section will present the models domains extent, the available measurements used for models' validation, the model input data (bathymetry, atmospheric forcing, and boundary conditions) and the models setup. The complete description of these models' implementation and validation are publicly available through the [MOODv2 Web App \(metocean-on-demand.com\)](https://metocean-on-demand.com).

The 2D Hydrodynamic model was implemented with the MIKE21 Flow Model Flexible Mesh (FM) version 2024 [10]. This is a modelling system for two-dimensional (2D) free-surface depth-averaged flows that is developed and maintained by DHI and offered as part of MIKE Powered by DHI². The model system is based on the numerical solution of the 2D incompressible Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes equations subject to the assumptions of Boussinesq and hydrostatic pressure.

The wave model was implemented with the version 2024 of MIKE 21 SW Spectral Wave FM model [11] developed and maintained by DHI and offered as part of MIKE Powered by DHI. The wave model simulates the growth, decay and transformation of wind-generated waves and swells in offshore and coastal areas.

3.1 Model Domains and Bathymetry

The model domains were designed to cover the main offshore wind farm (OWF) projects with open request for environmental license in Brazil (as for 18-01-2024 according to IBAMA) and the planned offshore areas in Uruguay according to National Fuel, Alcohol and Portland Administration (ANCAP, in Spanish). Due to the great extension of the interest area, two domains were defined, one covering the northern Brazilian coast (BR_N) and one covering the southeast/south Brazilian coast plus the Uruguay OWF interest areas (BR_S). Figure 3 presents the mesh model domains extent and the location of the available measurements used for the model's validation. The BR_N model spans from longitudes 50°W to 22°W and latitudes 10°S to 2°N. The BR_S model spans from longitudes 58°W to 32°W and latitudes 42°S to 14°S. The spatial discretization of both models uses an unstructured flexible mesh with varying resolution from coarse elements offshore (~27km) to finer elements near the coastline (~3 km).

The bathymetry information for the generation of each model mesh was sourced from the C-MAP database³, derived from local nautical charts, complemented with GEBCO-2021 database⁴, with 15 arc seconds resolution, which corresponds to ±450 m. For the land boundary data, high-resolution data from GSHHS⁵ was used.

² The user guide and scientific documentation of all MIKE21 models and modules can be found here: [MIKE 21 Documentation \(mikepoweredbydhi.help\)](https://mikepoweredbydhi.help)

³ <https://www.mikepoweredbydhi.com/products/mike-c-map>

⁴ https://www.gebco.net/about-us/news-and-events/gebco_08_release.html

⁵ <https://www.ngdc.noaa.gov/mgg/shorelines/gshhs.html>

Figure 3: Regional spectral wave and 2D hydrodynamical model meshes domain and bathymetry and the offshore wind projects planned for Brazil and Uruguay.

3.2 Available Measurements

The wave measurements used for the calibration of the spectral wave models were obtained from PNBOIA (11 stations), SIMCosta (1 station), and RedeOndas (4 station), which contain data for different measuring stations for the period 2002-2023, depending on the station and source. The datasets contain Significant Wave Height (H_{m0}), Mean Wave Direction (MWD), and Peak Wave Period (T_p), depending on the station and source. The location and complete description of all stations used for validation can be found in the validation reports accessible through the MOOD Web portal.

Water level datasets were obtained from SIMCosta (7 stations), IBGE-RMPG (4 station) and GLOSS (1 station), which contain data for different measuring stations for the period 2001-2023, depending on the station and source. For the present study, twelve (12) stations were used for the water level validations.

Current datasets were obtained from SIMCosta project. The number of available measurements for current is significantly smaller when compared to water levels measurements, therefore the assessment of the HD model current field is slightly more restricted to those specific areas where measurements are available. For the present study, two (2) stations were used for the current validations.

Additionally, altimetry data was used to validate modelled wave heights (H_{m0}) for the period from 2013 to 2023. The altimetry data were obtained from European Space Agency (ESA⁶) as pre-processed data made available via Marine Observation Data (dhigroup.com).

3.3 Hydrodynamic Model Setup

The 2D Hydrodynamic model uses the fifth generation ECMWF reanalysis (ERA5) wind and pressure fields as atmospheric forcing [12]. The boundary conditions rely on the global ocean tide model DTU10 from the Technical University of Denmark, which was developed based on FES2004 (Finite Element Solutions) and the 'response method' [13] using the latest seventeen years multi-mission measurements from TOPEX/POSEIDON (phase A and phase B), Jason-1 (phase A and phase B) and Jason-2 satellite altimetry for sea level residuals analysis, the harmonic coefficients correspond to the new global ocean tide model are developed [14]. For the bed resistance a varying Manning number has been applied. The Manning number were based on the map of surface sediments of the Brazilian Continental Shelf published by the Geological Survey of Brazil [15]. The Hydrodynamic models include the main riverine discharges, including, but not limited to, the Amazon and Pará river for the northern model domain, the Paraíba do Sul, Itajaí-Açú, Doce, Plata River and the Patos Lagoon discharges for the southern model domain. These sources are specified as daily discharges time series and are based on Global Flood Awareness System (GloFAS)⁷.

The final hydrodynamic setup for both domains (BR_N and BR_S) was based on an extensive calibration/validation process against available measurements within the study domain and DHI's expertise. The model setup was 2D barotropic, with wind forcing based on ERA5 wind fields. Tidal potential was included, and the boundary conditions were derived from the DTU10 global ocean tide model, implemented as Flather conditions with pressure corrections. Detailed information about the model setup can be found on the MOOD web portal.

3.4 Spectral Wave Model Setup

From DHI's experience, the use of ERA5 winds yields accurate wave conditions during normal optional wind speed ranges up to ~10-12 m/s, but generates an underestimation of the peak wave events. As such, ERA5 wind speeds larger than $WS_{10>12}$ m/s were modified by DHI in the wind fields used to force the wave model as an intermediate calibration step that goes into the numerical wave model. The ERA5 wind model used as atmospheric forcing for the spectral wave model is called 'ERA5 modified', and the details on the correction/calibration of the model are given in [16]. The offshore open boundaries were obtained from DHI's Global Wave Model [17], which provided directional spectra along the open boundaries. The water levels were obtained directly from the BR_S and BR_N hydrodynamic models. The ocean currents were derived from Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS) global reanalysis and analysis product⁸ and accounts for mesoscale and tidal spatially and temporally varying current. Both water level and current were included as an input to the spectral wave model to account for such spatial and temporal variations.

The regional wave model's setup was based on an extensive calibration/validation process against available wave measurements within the study domain and DHI's expertise. The model setup considered

⁶ [European Space Agency \(esa.int\)](https://esa.int)

⁷ [River discharge and related historical data from the Global Flood Awareness System](#)

⁸ [CMEMS-GLO-PUM-001-030.pdf \(copernicus.eu\)](#) and [CMEMS-GLO-PUM-001-024.pdf \(copernicus.eu\)](#)

a fully spectral in-stationary mode, with wind forcing based on ERA5-Modified wind fields. The parameterizations for the source terms for wind input and dissipation terms were based on Arduin et al. (2010) [18], and the boundary conditions were 2D action density spectra varying in time and along a line from DHI's Global Wave Model. Detailed information about the model setup can be found on the MOOD web portal.

4. Results

The regional atlas has been available on DHI's Metocean-on-Demand Web portal (MOODv2 Web App (metocean-on-demand.com) since April 2024, featuring the results of high-resolution hydrodynamic and spectral wave models for Brazil's coastal regions, particularly in the OWFs region. The models accurately represented the main patterns reported in the literature, such as the influence of frontal systems on water level, currents, and waves in the south-southeast region. They also captured the seasonal wave field patterns in the northern region, especially the impact of the seasonal shift of the ITCZ. Additionally, the models provided an improved representation of wave height in the northern region compared to available global datasets, with respect to the influence of the North Brazil Current on the wave field. Selected results and validation are presented below. As an example, Figure 4 presents the average Significant Wave Height between the years 2017 and 2018 in the model domains. For full access to all results, consult the MOOD portal.

4.1 Available Data

The available spectral wave model results comprise all relevant bulk parameters for the total spectrum as well as for the swell and wind sea partition. The hydrodynamic model results comprise water level, current speed, and direction. Hourly results are available for every grid point from Jan-1993 to Dec-2023 (Table 1).

Table 1: Regional Atlas output description

Metadata	Description	
Available Variables	Spectral Wave Model Significant Wave Height (Hm0), [m] Peak Wave Period (Tp), [s] Mean Wave Period (T01), [s] Zero-crossing Wave Period (T02), [s] Peak Wave Direction (PWD), [Deg. N. (coming from)] Mean Wave Direction (MWD), [Deg. N. (coming from)] Directional Standard Deviation (DSD), [degree] * All variables from Total spectrum, Swell and Sea	2D Hydrodynamic Model Water Level (WL) [m] Current Speed (CS) [m/s] Current Direction (CD) [Deg. N. (going-to)]
Temporal range and resolution	Hourly output. Start date; 1993-01-01 12:00:00 AM; End Date: 2023-12-31 11:00:00 PM	
Geographical Resolution	3 km coastal areas to 27 km offshore boundary	

The full wave spectra are available for specific pre-defined output points, with 0.5 degrees resolution up to approximately 200 km from the coastline and with 2 degrees resolution in the open ocean – especially suited for nesting local coastal and estuarine spectral wave models.

Figure 4: Example of the Spectral Wave Model results statistics (mean Significant Wave Height) covering all OWF projects over Brazilian and Uruguayan waters.

4.2 Results Validation

The complete set of validation plots for all available stations are presented in the validation reports publicly available at the MOOD Web portal (MOODv2 Web App (metocean-on-demand.com)). In this chapter a summary of the comparison statistics is presented for all available stations, as well as some examples of scatter comparison plots.

Additionally, satellite derived H_{m0} comparisons were assessed enabling a spatial assessment of the spectral wave model accuracy over the model domains. The altimetry comparison was done by calculating the spatially varying bias for H_{m0} in bins of 0.5×0.5 degrees, for 2013-2023 (11 years).

As shown in Figure 5, the developed spectral wave model presents a very low BIAS over the entire domain, showing an improved behavior when compared to the performance of the global reanalysis from ECMWF (ERA5) at these regions. This was achieved through a combination of factors such as considering the time and spatially varying current field in the wave propagation terms and the detailed calibration of the air-sea interaction parameters as well as the bottom friction specification and enhanced grid resolution.

Figure 6 presents an example of scatter plots and dual-rose plots comparing the modelled and measured data for Current Speed and Significant Wave Height for two chosen stations. An excellent agreement both for the energy and direction can be noted for both stations and variables. The complete set of validation plots for all available stations are presented in the validation reports, accessible through the MOOD Web portal.

Table 2, Table 3 and Table 4 present the summary of the quality indexes - BIAS, Correlation Coefficient (CC), RMSE and Peak Ratio (PR) - for all compared stations that cover most of the domain. It should be noted that the South/South-East domain is more densely populated with available stations. For H_{m0} , the mean RMSE is 0.26, the average BIAS is 0.03 m, average CC is 0.91 and the average Peak Ratio is 1.01. For T_p , the mean RMSE is 1,91 s, the average BIAS is 0.06 s, average CC is 0.68 and the average Peak Ratio is 1.1. For current speed, the mean RMSE is 0.14 m/s, the average BIAS is 0.01 m/s, average CC is 0.63 and the average Peak Ratio is 1.05. For water level, the mean RMSE is 0.11 m, the average BIAS is 0.02 m, average CC is 0.93 and the average Peak Ratio is 1.02.

Overall, a highly satisfactory validation was achieved for all observed variables considering the available observations. The dataset can be considered well suited for assessing both the operational and extreme conditions throughout the domains. It is important to highlight that the focus of the calibration effort was towards the OWF project's main regions, and therefore, the dataset must be used with caution elsewhere. For example, results pertaining to areas near the Amazon River mouth, Marajo Bay, and Sao Marcos Bay should be interpreted with caution due to the incomplete representation of estuarine processes in these regions, such as baroclinic pressure gradients.

Figure 5: H_{m0} comparison of altimetry data and model results showing Bias (top panel) and Scatter Index (bottom panel). Comparison for the period of 2013-01-01 to 2023-12-31.

Figure 6: Scatter plots and dual-rose plots of modelled against measured data. In the top panel, current speed comparison for RS-4 station (a and b) and in the lower panel, H_{m0} comparison for Rio Grande station (c and d).

Table 2: Statistical parameters of H_{m0} [m] and T_p [s] considering the validation stations. The table shows the statistical parameters (N, BIAS, AME, RMSE, SI, EV, CC, PR) considering the validation stations for H_{m0} [m].

Station Name	Hm0				Tp			
	BIAS [m]	RMSE [m]	CC	PR	BIAS [s]	RMSE [s]	CC	PR
Fortaleza	0.03	0.17	0.89	0.91	0.96	2.30	0.76	1.24
Recife	0.21	0.26	0.91	1.04	1.42	2.82	0.40	1.21
noronha	0.22	0.27	0.88	0.99	1.51	2.66	0.32	1.34
pernambuco	0.14	0.18	0.94	1.00	0.06	1.67	0.69	1.11
Vitoria	0.08	0.19	0.93	0.96	-0.01	1.73	0.76	1.10
Itaguaí	-0.09	0.23	0.93	0.84	-0.10	1.72	0.72	1.12
Cabofrio2	0.06	0.25	0.92	1.07	0.08	1.39	0.84	1.10
alcatrazes	-0.22	0.3	0.95	1.10	-0.39	1.76	0.73	1.17
Santos-bm01	0.00	0.28	0.93	1.10	0.05	1.73	0.73	1.05
Santos-ax24	-0.02	0.22	0.95	1.08	0.01	1.54	0.78	0.93
Floripa	-0.10	0.28	0.89	1.02	-1.24	2.05	0.69	1.00
Tramandai	0.01	0.18	0.92	0.92	0.34	2.01	0.60	1.02
Rio Grande	0.02	0.31	0.93	1.17	-0.19	1.30	0.79	1.10
RS-5	-0.03	0.21	0.91	0.85	-0.40	1.88	0.73	1.08
Cassino	0.25	0.43	0.81	0.90	-0.87	2.71	0.58	1.07
Minuano	-0.13	0.34	0.94	1.13	-0.28	1.30	0.80	1.03
MEAN	0.03	0.26	0.91	1.01	0.06	1.91	0.68	1.10

Table 3: Statistical parameters of WL [m] considering the validation stations. The table shows the statistical parameters (N, BIAS, AME, RMSE, SI, EV, CC, PR) considering the validation stations for WL [m].

Station Name	BIAS [m]	RMSE [m]	CC	PR
Pecem	0.03	0.08	0.99	0.96
fort	0.03	0.08	1.00	0.95
Suape	0.00	0.08	0.99	0.90
maca	0.00	0.10	0.96	0.99
arca	0.02	0.08	0.97	0.99
DHN	0.01	0.11	0.94	1.01
ubatuba	0.01	0.10	0.95	1.01
Ilhabela	0.02	0.11	0.95	1.05
imbi	0.01	0.15	0.87	1.11
Imbituba	-0.02	0.13	0.91	1.11
Tramandai	0.02	0.15	0.84	1.05
Rio_Grande_2	0.09	0.20	0.76	1.05
MEAN	0.02	0.11	0.93	1.02

Table 4: Statistical parameters of CS [m/s] considering the validation stations. The table shows the statistical parameters (N, BIAS, AME, RMSE, SI, EV, CC, PR) considering the validation stations for CS [m/s].

Station Name	BIAS [m/s]	RMSE [m/s]	CC	PR
RS-4_ANT	-0.01	0.15	0.63	1.16
RS-5	0.02	0.13	0.63	0.94
MEAN	0.01	0.14	0.63	1.05

4.3 Accessing the Data

The regional atlas results can be accessed through the [MOODv2 Web App \(metocean-on-demand.com\)](https://moodv2.metoccean-on-demand.com) DHI's portal for ordering metocean data. The DHI's interactive WEB portal offers metocean data on demand (ocean, waves, and atmosphere) for global and high-resolution regional models (Figure 7). The metadata as well as the complete validation reports are available for consultation.

Figure 7: Snapshot of the interactive MOOD (Metocean-On-Demand) DHI's WEB portal for ordering metocean data. The portal offers global and high-resolution regional metocean models results, as well as providing analytics for time series, such as rose plot, scatter plot, statistics, and extreme values (highlighted).

6. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The development of the regional spectral wave and 2D hydrodynamic models in this study successfully achieved comprehensive coverage of the Brazilian and Uruguayan coasts. The domains, divided into northern and southern/southeastern regions, were designed to capture the distinct oceanographic and meteorological characteristics of these areas. This strategic division ensured accurate representation of the diverse conditions influencing offshore wind farm (OWF) projects, providing a robust framework for current and future offshore energy initiatives.

Validation of the models against extensive measurement data, including wave parameters, water level, and current, demonstrated high accuracy and reliability. The results indicated minimal biases and errors, affirming the models' precision in simulating real-world conditions. The use of satellite altimetry data further validated the wave height results across the entire domain.

Future studies should focus on improving the representation of estuarine processes, such as baroclinic pressure gradients, particularly in areas like the Amazon and Plata River mouths and São Marcos Bay. Enhancing these aspects will increase the models' accuracy in these regions and adjacent coastal areas. Additionally, incorporating climate change projections in new simulations will provide valuable insights into future metocean conditions, helping assess the long-term viability and resilience of offshore energy projects under changing climatic conditions.

The availability of high-quality metocean data through the MOOD portal significantly enhances the potential for Front-End Engineering Design (FEED) studies. Detailed representation of metocean conditions supports more accurate and efficient design processes, contributing to the overall feasibility, safety, and economic viability of these projects.

The MOOD portal (Figure 7) is the to-go online platform for accessing comprehensive metocean data generated by these models. By offering an interactive and user-friendly interface, the portal facilitates the retrieval of relevant data for various applications. The inclusion of validation reports and metadata ensures transparency and aids users in understanding the context and reliability of the data provided.

In conclusion, the regional spectral wave and 2D hydrodynamic models developed in this study provide a highly accurate and comprehensive metocean dataset for the Brazilian and Uruguayan coasts. Validation against extensive measurement data confirms their reliability and precision, making them a valuable resource for offshore energy projects. The data, accessible through the MOOD portal, supports FEED studies and other applications, promoting the efficient and economic development of offshore energy solutions.

REFERENCES

- [1] IMarEST, "Metocean Procedures Guide for Offshore Renewable," no. 2, p. 26, 2018.
- [2] EPE, "Geração Eólica Offshore: Considerações sobre a limitação de área a ser cedida," *NOTA TÉCNICA EPE/DEE/035/2023-R1*, 2024.
- [3] EPE, "Geração Eólica Offshore: Considerações sobre valor devido à União pela cessão de área," *NOTA TÉCNICA EPE/DEE/036/2023-R1*, 2024.
- [4] R. N. Candella, "Characteristics of ocean waves off Fortaleza, CE, Brazil, extracted from 1-year deep-water measured data," *Ocean Dynamics* 69, pp. 1239–1251. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10236-019-01293-z>, 2019.
- [5] C. P. Dereczynski and W. F. Menezes, "Meteorologia da Bacia de Campos," *In: Martins, R.P., Grossmann-Matheson, G.S., editores. Meteorologia e Oceanografia. Rio de Janeiro: Elsevier. Habitats, v. 2., pp. 1-54*, 2015.
- [6] H. Rapizo, T. H. Durrant and A. V. Babanin, "An assessment of the impact of surface currents on wave modeling in the Southern Ocean," *Ocean Dynamics* 68, pp. 939-955. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10236-018-1171-7>, 2018.
- [7] H. Hersbach, B. Bell, P. Berrisford, S. . Hirahara, A. Horányi, J. Muñoz-Sabater, ... and J.-N. Thépaut, "The ERA5 global reanalysis.," *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, vol. 146, no. 730, pp. 1999-2049. <https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.3803>, 2020.
- [8] B. M. Castro, F. P. Brandini, A. M. S. Pires-Vanin and L. B. Miranda, "Multidisciplinary oceanographic processes on the Western Atlantic continental shelf between 4 N and 34 S," in *The Sea*, Cambridge, Harvard University Press, 2006, pp. 1-39.
- [9] M. Dottori and B. M. Castro, "The response of the Sao Paulo Continental Shelf, Brazil, to synoptic winds," *Ocean dynamics*, vol. 59, no. 4, pp. 603-614, 2009.
- [10] DHI A/S, "MIKE 21 FLOW MODEL FM Hydrodynamic Module, Scientific Documentation," DHI, Hørsholm, 2024.
- [11] DHI A/S, "MIKE 21 SPECTRAL WAVE MODULE Scientific Documentation," 2024.
- [12] H. Hersbach, B. Bell, P. Berrisford, G. Biavati, A. Horányi, J. Muñoz Sabater, J. Nicolas, C. Peubey, R. Radu, I. Rozum, D. Schepers, A. Simmons, C. Soci, D. Dee and J.-N. Thépaut, "ERA5 hourly data on single levels from 1940 to present," Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (CDS), 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.24381/cds.adbb2d47>. [Accessed 12 December 2023].
- [13] W. H. Munk and D. E. Cartwright, "Tidal Spectroscopy and Prediction," *Philos. Trans. R. Soc.*, London, 1966.
- [14] O. B. A. Yongcun Cheng, "Improvement of global ocean tide models," in *Altimetry for Oceans and Hydrology OST-ST Meeting*, Technical University of Denmark, 2010.
- [15] G. T. d. M. Dias, M. Robrini, J. S. S. Freire and A. Figueiredo, "Geologia dos sedimentos superficiais da plataforma continental brasileira," CPRM, Brasília, DF, 2007.
- [16] DHI A/S, "ERA5 Wind: Validation and Comparison. Project Nr. 11826846, Final 1.0," 2023.
- [17] DHI A/S, "Global Atlas of Siting Parameters Offshore: DHI Global Wave Model: Set-up, Calibration and Validation," 2023.
- [18] F. Ardhuin, E. Rogers, A. V. Babanin, J.-F. Filipot, R. Magne, ... and F. Collard, "Semiempirical Dissipation Source Functions for Ocean Waves. Part I: Definition, Calibration, and Validation," *American Meteorological Society*, vol. 40, no. 9, pp. 1917 - 1941, 2010.